

An Analytical Study of Extension Strategies as Competitiveness Tools for FPOs: A Case Study of Savitribai Phule Goat Farmer Producers Company Ltd, Sinnar Dist: Nashik

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Abstract:

Farmers' cooperatives, or FPOs, are primarily made up of small and marginal farmers (between 70 and 80 per cent of members). Under the Producers' Company & Cooperative Act, section 8 Company Act, Society Act, and Trust Act, over 10,000 FPOs have been registered. The study evaluates the components of extension strategic interventions necessary to achieve competitiveness and improved business performance of FPOs using a case-based methodology and a literature review. The study aims to use the APP (Asset-Process Performance) paradigm to investigate how competitiveness is derived from efficient extension tactics. The Maharashtra-based Savitribai Phule Goat Farmer Producers Company Ltd. (SPGFPC) has been analyzed using this paradigm.

Keywords: Farmer producer organizations, determinants, welfare, small and marginal farmers

Introduction:

Although it is mainly produced on many dispersed small properties, agriculture is vital to the Indian economy. It employs about 56% of India's workforce, boosts the country's economy overall, and lowers poverty by giving most people jobs and food security. However, small-holding-based agriculture has steadily lost viability due to highly dispersed, diverse, and fragmented landholding, growing cultivation costs, and small/marginal farmers' (SF/MF) restricted access to public resources and markets. High reliance on farmers has been caused by several factors, including limited output volumes, a lack of public resources, high-quality inputs, financial facilities, current technology, frequent crop failures, an unreliable market, income security, and a poorly organized supply chain.

A variety of collective services, including the management of rural infrastructure, the sale of agricultural goods or necessary production inputs, and the administration of common property, are provided by Producers. Collectives are community-based and community-driven organizations that have gained popularity as a way to help resource-poor farmers improve their living conditions. Farmers lose out on large-scale, mechanized equipment, economies of scale, and credit/finance as their landholdings shrink. Additionally, the capacity to sell produce and negotiate a fair price is severely constrained. Thus, the country's agricultural sector has a compelling case for collectivization (Ramappa K. 2018).

The Indian government has implemented several development initiatives to organize farmers into various types of producers' collectives. The Cooperative movement (since the 1900s), Self-Help Groups (since the 1980s), Farmers Clubs, Joint Liability Groups, Federations of SHGs, Common Interest Groups (CIGs), and so on are the most well-known among them. The 'Farmer Producers Organizations (FPOs)' are a hybrid model that combines the best aspects of corporate industry and cooperatives, and they have recently attracted renewed interest (Tripathy et al., 2020).

The main objective of these producer collectives is to create efficient and successful systems for the production, harvesting, aggregation, grading, storage, value-adding,

processing, marketing, export/import, sale, or supply of machinery, consumables, etc., for the whole agri-value chain. Professionals manage them, and member farmers and producers own and operate them. In the agricultural sector, the idea of FPOs is still relatively new, and it has received very little attention, especially from outside India. Therefore, the current study focuses on developing FPOs registered under the Producers Company Act of 2002 and 2013 and their governance, management, and mechanisms for fostering sustainability and competitiveness.

Research Methodology

The business models supporting the promotion of the institution's expansion strategies and the ensuing competitiveness in FPOs were examined in this study using a persuasive case study technique (Siggelkow, 2007). The study attempts to understand how effective extension strategies boost competitiveness using the APP framework (Momaya, 1998). Savitribai Phule Goat Farmer Producers Company Ltd. (SPGFPCL), located in the Nashik region of Maharashtra and backed and encouraged by Yuva Mitra NGO1, has been examined using this approach. The study uses primary and secondary data to accomplish the objectives above. Face-to-face meetings with the SPGFPCL's chairman, CEO, and employees occurred in January and February 2020. Some members were then contacted over the phone in May and June 2024.

Evolution of the FPC Movement in India

The Indian Companies Act of 1956 was revised in 2002, and a new chapter titled "Producers Company" was added in response to the Prof. Y. K. Alagh Committee's findings. Under the amended version, primary producers could unite under the cooperative institution's guiding concept of one man, one vote. Profitability may be the stated Company's goal for producing, gathering, acquiring, grading, combining, managing, marketing, selling, exporting, or importing goods or services. Like its traditional forebears, producer enterprises find developing value-added and marketing capabilities challenging due to this capital limitation. The producer company statute has been in effect for five years, but neither the government nor development organizations have attempted to increase public awareness of the idea or its application. The offer from this committee was made when many development agencies seemed to have found a means to organize producers in a market-oriented economy, and the concept was just beginning to acquire traction in producer implementation (Singh, 2008). Small and marginal landholding farmers can use FPCs to protect the worth of their products and the dignity of their labour, shielding them from hierarchical or captive value chains in the face of enormous corporate resources. However, this is insufficient, given the larger problem of inadequate food systems for most smallholders (Kalia, 2019).

Status of FPCs in India:

FPOs are farmers' collectives, and between 70 and 80 per cent of their members are small or marginal farmers. There are currently about 5000 FPOs (including FPCs) across the nation, established over the last eight to ten years under various efforts of the Indian government, including SFAC, state governments, NABARD, and other organizations. The remaining FPOs are registered as cooperatives, societies, etc., while about 32em are registered as producer companies. To sustain their business operations, the majority of these FPOs—whose shareholder membership ranges from 100 to over 1000 farmers—need handholding support; with a total budgetary outlay of Rs. 6,865 crores, the Indian government launched the Central Sector Scheme for "Formation and Promotion of 10,000 Farmer Producer Organizations (FPOs)" in 2020. The scheme aims to help farmers increase their bargaining power, take advantage of economies of scale, lower production costs, and

improve their incomes by aggregating their agricultural produce, contributing significantly to sustainable incomes.

Further, to strengthen PACS, a project for the Computerization of 63,000 functional PACS with a total financial outlay of ₹2,516 Crore has also been approved by the Government of India, which entails bringing all the functional PACS onto an ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning) based standard national software, linking them with NABARD through State Cooperative Banks (StCBs) and District Central Cooperative Banks (DCCBs). The government has also approved a proposal to set up new multi-purpose PACS or primary dairy/ fisheries cooperatives covering every Panchayat/ village in the next five years, with the support of the National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD), National Dairy Development Board (NDDB), National Fisheries Development Board (NFDB), National Cooperative Development Corporation (NCDC) and other National level Federations. Ministry of Cooperation has taken various other initiatives to provide cooperatives with requisite forward and backward linkages to market agri produce, obtain credit and other services at the Panchayat/ village level, and generate multiple and stable revenue streams for them, thus making them self-reliant. Additionally, SFAC has launched numerous projects to improve FPC operations and economic results by connecting them to markets in collaboration with the corporate, cooperative, and private sectors and relevant technologies. State Level Producers Companies (SLPCs) were established as the State level umbrella organization for their individual State FPCs to strengthen and broaden their backward and forward linkages. Eight SLPCs operate in Gujarat, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Telangana, Uttar Pradesh, and West Bengal. They are seen to be a successful way to address the functional issues that FPCs face. Among the many goals they aim to achieve are: a) better coordination amongst the FPCs established in the State; b) assistance in initiating policy discussions with State and Central agencies; c) availability and accessibility of services and inputs; d) cost-effective capacity-building; e) facilitating financial institution credit support; and f) taking advantage of opportunities to strengthen backwards and forward linkages. Accruing producers' farmers into collectives is acknowledged as a 'best fit' for lowering agricultural risk and enhancing access to markets, technology, and credit, given the present statistics of Indian agriculture in general and farmers in particular. As a result, various communal structures have developed throughout the nation, each with advantages and disadvantages that several studies and publications have emphasized.

In contrast, the more contemporary FPC model is viewed as a more formal type of business organization, with the expectation that it will effectively and efficiently develop the member farmers' backward and forward links, increasing their revenue. In India, more than 8,500 FPCs have been advertised. It has been noted that only 12–15% of businesses are operational, with the remaining companies finding it difficult to simplify their operations, which also contributes to inter-regional disparities. As we encourage more FPCs in the future, these businesses will have a tough road ahead for expansion and survival. Owners and operators of these businesses are farmers, particularly smallholder farmers. As a result, creating a farmer producers association is a process-driven endeavour that requires careful, sympathetic, and collaborative preparation and execution to concentrate on fostering a sense of ownership and belonging among current and prospective members.

'Governance' and management concerns require more focus. These businesses differ from standard business structures because they have a significant social component that aims to improve farmers' lives and forward the cause of rural development. These hybrid firms fall into the "social enterprises" category because of their strong social orientation and economic

focus. They use a "Community Driven Development" (CDD) method to address socioeconomic and developmental challenges

The study attempts to provide an answer to the question of how competitiveness in FPOs is influenced by effective extension tactics against the backdrop of these characteristics. The second section, which follows this introduction, examines the literature on the topic. The research technique used for the study is covered in the third section. A case study of Savitribai Phule Goat Farmer Producers Company Ltd. (SPGFPCL), the first female FPC in Asia, is presented in the fourth section, and the study's conclusion is covered in the fifth.

Sustainability of Farmer Producer Organizations

Goat farming is not only a source of income for small and marginal farmers in rural Sinnar, Maharashtra, but also an insurance policy. Goats, sometimes called the "poor man's cow," are a reliable source of revenue even in regions prone to drought since they can survive in difficult conditions and on low-fertility grounds. Goats have been a lifeline for many households in this area, where water scarcity hinders agricultural pursuits. However, only through scientific methods and group efforts will goat farming reach its full potential. Savitribai Phule Goat Farming Producer Company Ltd. fills that needed gap. With the help of NABARD, Yuva Mitra founded this women-owned business, which has grown to be a ray of light in Sinnar, empowering underprivileged women via sustainable goat rearing.

Developing Sustainable Goat Farming to Empower Rural Women

To raise the income of underprivileged and assetless goat-rearing women, Savitribai Phule Goat Farming Producer Company Ltd. was established in May 2016. Due of its history of water scarcity and drought, Sinnar became the centre of this effort. With more than 1100 stockholders and more than 2500 members, the Company is wholly owned and run by women.

- a) **Establishing Sustainable Sources of Income:** The Company's primary goal is to make goat farming a viable business for underprivileged women, particularly widows and single women. This is accomplished by raising awareness, sharing knowledge, and using reasonably priced technologies in goat husbandry. The business specializes on Osmanabadi and Sangamneri breeds, which are ideal for the regional climate.
- b) **All-inclusive Services:** The following services are provided to members of Savitribai Phule Goat Farming Producer Company Ltd.:
- c) **Goat Insurance:** To offer a safety net in the event of goat mortality, members are connected with appropriate insurance providers. In order to guarantee that members receive the assistance they require, the organization expedites the settlement of claims.
- d) **Marketing:** The organization actively promotes goater-based goods made by its members. Currently, it sells goat meat and milk under the "SAVI" brand, guaranteeing that members' produce is sold at fair pricing.
- e) **Product Line:** The Company sells various goods, such as raw milk, ghee, yoghurt, and cheese (Cheddar, Feta).
- f) **Weight-Based Goat Trading:** The Company used weight-based goat trading to reduce distress sales, which ensures greater pricing for members' goats depending on weight. Market exploitation has decreased as a result of this endeavour.
- g) **Knowledge Support:** Members are taught superior fodder management techniques and given high-quality bucks for breeding. The corporation encourages the production of silage, concentrated feed, and fodder crops to counteract summer stress.

- h) Financial Support:** By connecting all members to the official banking system, financial literacy is encouraged. The purpose of Joint Liability Groups is to assist one another in obtaining credit.
- i) Veterinary Services:** To provide essential goat treatment, the organization sets up paraveterinary cadres known as Pashu Sakhis at the local level. The goal of this project is to lower goat death rates.
- j) Pashu Mall:** The business runs 57 Pashu Malls in rural areas, giving goat farmers access to supplements and cutting down on transportation expenses.
- k) Nursery:** The Company runs a small-scale nursery that offers seedlings of the highly nutritious fodder plant Moringa (Drumstick) to meet the fodder shortage.

Influence and Achievement

Significant progress has been made in empowering women and enhancing their standard of living by Savitribai Phule Goat Farming Producer Company Ltd. The organization guarantees fair rates for members' produce through creative methods like weight-based goat trade. In addition to helping members, the launch of goat milk selling has opened up the highly sought-after metropolitan Market. Additionally, the Company's emphasis on veterinary care, financial inclusion, and knowledge sharing has improved goat farming methods and decreased death rates, raising shareholders' overall revenue. In Sinnar, Maharashtra, Savitribai Phule Goat Farming Producer Company Ltd. is a testament to the transformational potential of sustainable goat farming, empowering women and bolstering rural communities. This women-owned business is building a better future for all of its members by emphasizing teamwork and scientific methods.

Performance (total social impact and net income):

The FPO's formation has benefited its female members in several ways. For their goat, members are receiving a better and guaranteed price. Because of the guaranteed marketing facilities, many individual members also use bank financing to expand their grocery operations. Women members have escaped the intermediaries's debt trap. They oversee all aspects of the Company's operations, including marketing, processing, and collection. Many women members have improved their abilities, leadership traits, self-confidence, and self-esteem due to the ongoing encouragement and methodical, incremental treatments. There are roughly 8000 active members out of the approximately 1040 total members. These individuals are dispersed among a single, sizable block of 30 GPs. The sale of goat milk and meat has increased member incomes; FPC is selling 50 litres of goat milk per week to ABC Farm in Pune and local markets under the SAHAJ brand, and they intend to expand the value chain by building their own slaughterhouse.

Governance & Managerial Capabilities:

The BoD members came from different villages from the 30 GPs of one large district Block. While the procurement process was in order, the members did not know all the BoD members of the FPO. The POPI fully backs the managerial capacity. The BoD members did not seem to be involved much in the operations and management of the FPO. The operations are primarily managed by the managers appointed by the POPI, Yuva Mitra. As a state-level nodal agency for training and capacity building, Yuva Mitra has the workforce and competence to operate the FPO successfully. While the BoD members seemed very committed to the FPO business, they did not seem to be ready to operate the FPO on their own. The large geographic spread of the FPO, which has over 30 GPs, can make it difficult for the FPO to be operated by any of the current women BoD members. This operation will most likely require a professional agency like Yuva Mitra to run it. Women leaders from the

FPO must be identified, trained, and handed over by Yuva Mitra to operate the FPO independently.

Nature of Technologies (Cost & Ease of Operation):

The FPO has adopted appropriate technologies. The technologies adopted in cattle/goat rearing, cattle feed, vermin compost, vermin wash, etc., are simple, natural, and easily understood by the producer members. Though the processing technology of goat milk and cheese making is the standard technology, these processes are not understood by the producer members or members of the BoD. The small processing unit is managed by a couple of technicians and the person who buys the product from the FPO. The buyer appoints his experts to ensure quality cheese and other milk products from the processing unit.

Conclusion

In building sustainable institutions, the number of indicators plays an essential role. Starting with the 'geo-demography', farmers have a sound understanding of business and a spirit of entrepreneurship. History says that three years is insufficient to establish a sustainable grassroots institution. As a process-driven activity, it takes almost one and a half years to convince farmers and register the FPO in the right way and spirit. Promoting institution management skills and understanding the socio-cultural aspects has implications for bringing cohesiveness and ownership among members. There is a need for an enabling ecosystem for the promotion & formation, financing, and marketing of FPO products and services. The extent of technology adoption for value addition and processing is the need of the hour. Networking and liaising with technical institutions like ICAR and SAU sin, including KVKs, would help FPOs understand technical know-how. This has also been exemplified in the present case; having linkages with ICAR-CIRG has enhanced productivity in the grocery business. The foundation of any company organization is its management and governance. SPGFPCCL has established and adhered to sound management and governance procedures. The key success factors were the Company's transparent and accountable board, the chairman's transformative leadership, the involvement of all members and board members in all meetings and activities, the professionalism and skill of the management team, and so forth.

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